

Stirling's Approximation and Information Theory?

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Stirling's approximation, $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n) - n$ for large n , is often obtained using the method of steepest descent (i.e. saddle point). We suggest that for $n \rightarrow \infty$, one may obtain the term $n \ln(n)$ in two ways from information theory and even directly without any use of the \ln function. The connection with information theory may be established because factorials appear in an expression for the number of permutations $N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!$ which may be evaluated in an $n \rightarrow \infty$ limit, which in turn is linked to an average probability which may be expressed in terms of products of probabilities to the power $N p(e_i)$. Alternatively, one may consider maximizing \ln of the number of permutations subject to a constraint of $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. We suggest that one already knows the solution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ from information theory and so this forces an $n \rightarrow \infty$ form on $\ln(n!)$. We also argue that there is no need to extremize the \ln of the number of permutations. One may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann result by simply maximizing the number of permutations.

Finally we consider evaluating $n!$ directly in the $n \rightarrow \infty$ limit.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and Information Theory

We argue that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-e_i/T)$ follows directly from considerations of information. The simplest way to examine the situation is to consider two particles with energy e_1 and e_2 which collide elastically. It is then known that the outcome e_i, e_j satisfies:

$$E_i + e_j = e_1 + e_2 \quad ((1))$$

The question is whether there is any bias, i.e. whether all e_i, e_j sets have the same probability. If one suggests that there is equal probability, the next step is to compute the combined probability for e_i, e_j . From probability theory, if all particles are independent, then:

$$P(e_i, e_j) = p(e_i)p(e_j) \quad ((2))$$

Using ((1)) and ((2)) leads to $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ where C and T are constants and the minus sign is chosen so that there is a decreasing probability to have a high energy.

We argue that implicit in the assumption of independence is the notion of a very large number of particles. In fact, this limit may be taken to be infinite. If there are a finite number of particles (not too large), the total energy is constrained to E and even if $n-1$ particles are independent, the last particle has its energy fixed and so cannot be independent.

((1)) is based on collisions of two particles, but it is really a statement about energy distribution. We suggest one may apply the same information theoretic ideas to the total energy E . In other words, one may have E break into:

sets $\{e_i\}$ such that $\sum_i e_i = E$. ((3))

This is the microcanonical picture.

In such a case, the number of particles in each set is N , but some particles may have $e_i=0$. If all sets have equal weight, a standard assumption in statistical mechanics, then one assumes particle independence. We suggest, however, that one requires $N \rightarrow \infty$ for this because if one assigns energies independently to $n-1$ particles, the n th particle has its energy fixed.

The next step seems to consider probabilities $p(e_i)$ and $N \rightarrow \infty$. The $N \rightarrow \infty$ case is special because one expects that each e_i particle (with probability $p(e_i)$) appear:

$N p(e_i)$ times ((4)) This represents independence

This, however, is an average approach. It cuts out solutions from the microcanonical picture such as $(0,0,\dots, E/2,E/2)$ etc which still add to E . In other words, one seems to start with the superset $\{e_i\}$ and then uses this to find $p(e_i)$ which must be calculated somehow. Next, one considers trial runs of $N \rightarrow \infty$ trials, using ideas of probability, i.e. the canonical approach. This leads to a reduced set with each e_i appearing $N p(e_i)$ times. One may write the probability for such an average element:

Probability of a particular average trial run = $\prod_i p(e_i)^{N p(e_i)}$ ((5))

((5)) indicates the independence of probabilities, so we suggest that $N \rightarrow \infty$ to guarantee this.

What does it mean to say: a particular average trial run in ((5))? Given that $N p(e_i)$ is the number of outcomes of e_i , one may still consider permutations. Each of these permutations represents the same probability. We suggest that the feature each permutation has in common is $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E$. Thus, like in the two particle collision situation ((1)), ((2)), one knows that the probability $p(e_i)$ is:

$p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ ((6))

This, we argue, is consistent with the conservation of energy and probability independence. There is actually no need to maximize the \ln of the number of average number of permutations subject to an average energy scheme to obtain the MB distribution ((6)). There is, however, nothing wrong with considering the number of permutations, written using factorials, because one may deduce properties of $n!$ for $n \rightarrow \infty$, we suggest.

First Information Theoretic Approach to Stirling's Approximation

((5)) shows that the probability for a particular average set of $N \rightarrow \infty$ trial runs is a product of $p(e_i)$ to the power $N p(e_i)$. A probability, however, may be written as $1/\text{number of}$

possibilities. In the case of average trials runs, we suggest that the number of possibilities is the number of permutations i.e.

$$\text{Probability} = 1 / \{ N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)! \} \quad ((7))$$

((7)) contains factorial expressions, with $n(e_i) = N p(e_i)$. ((7)), however, must equal ((6)) which seems to suggest that in the $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ limit

$$(N p(e_i))! = p(e_i)^{\text{power } (N p(e_i))} \quad ((8))$$

A solution to ((8)) is to have: $(N p(e_i))! = (N p(e_i))^{\text{power } (N p(e_i))}$ in the $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ limit ((9))

because $\text{product over } i \ N^{\text{power } (N p(e_i))} = N^{\text{power } N}$, i.e. a constant. In other words, ((8)) yields the leading term of Stirling's approximation, which is the result for $N \rightarrow \text{infinite}$. This follows from information theoretic results and does not make use of the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution explicitly. We have argued, however, that the form ((6)) implicitly represents the solution $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$.

Stirling's Approximation and the MB Distribution Form

Another approach to find the leading term of Stirling's approximation is to consider the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution as known a priori (from ((6)) or from ((1)) and ((2))). The independence of probabilities suggests no bias (except that average energy is E), so one may consider maximizing the number of average trial run permutations ((7)) in order to obtain a maximum result subject to a constraint on average energy. A non-maximum result seems to imply an extra bias. Given that $\exp(-e/T)$ appears in the MB solution, one may take \ln of ((8)) for convenience. (We later show that \ln is not necessary.)

Maximize $\ln(N! / \text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)!) + b \text{ Sum over } i \ e_i n(e_i)$ ((10)) or

$$\text{Extremize } (- \ln(n(e_i)!)) + b e_i = 0 \text{ such that } n(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/b) \quad ((11))$$

This suggests that $d/dn(e_i) \{-\ln(n(e_i)!)\}$ should behave as constant $-\ln(n(e_i))$. A solution is immediately:

$$\ln(n(e_i)!) = n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) \text{ in the } n \rightarrow \text{infinite limit} \quad ((12))$$

Again, one obtains the first term of Stirling's approximation.

Traditionally, in statistical mechanics one takes the \ln of the number of permutations (or state etc). One may ask: Is it necessary to use \ln ? We argue that it is not. We consider a calculation which does not use \ln a priori.

We have seen in the above two sections that $n(e_i)! = n(e_i)^{\text{power } (n(e_i))}$ in the $n \rightarrow \text{infinite}$ limit.

Thus, one may maximize: $\prod_i n(e_i)^{n(e_i) + b} \sum_i e_i n(e_i)$.

The maximization involves $d/dn(e_i)$ for each $n(e_i)$, independently so:

$$\prod_{j \neq i} n(e_j)^{n(e_j)} \left\{ \frac{d}{dn(e_i)} \exp(-n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))) \right\} + b e_i = 0 \quad ((13))$$

$$\left\{ \frac{d}{dn(e_i)} \exp(-n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))) \right\} = n(e_i)^{n(e_i)} \{ 1 + \ln(n(e_i)) \} \quad \text{but}$$

$$\prod_{j \neq i} n(e_j)^{n(e_j)} n(e_i)^{n(e_i)} = \text{constant}$$

Taking the product removes e_i dependence. Thus:

$$C(1 + \ln(n)) + b e_i = 0 \quad \text{which leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann result.}$$

Direct Calculation of Stirling's Approximation

We suggest that one may obtain the leading term of Stirling's approximation: $n! = n^n e^{-n} \sqrt{2\pi n}$ in the $n \rightarrow \infty$ limit directly.

$$N! \text{ by definition is } N(N-1)(N-2) \dots 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 1 \quad ((14))$$

At one point $N-b$ will be approximately $N/2$. A number of subsequent factors will also be close to $N/2$. Then, they will become close to $N/3$ etc. The integers in the denominator, however, should cancel with numbers at the end of ((14)) e.g. $b(b-1) \dots 5 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 2 \cdot 1$. Thus, one might expect that:

$$n! = n^{n-b} \text{ where } b \text{ is some integer much smaller than } n.$$

Given that $n \rightarrow \infty$, $n-b$ approximates n and one ultimately has:

$$n! = n^n e^{-n} \quad ((15))$$

Another way to state this is that one may approximate $(N-b)$ by N/a_1 , $(N-b^2)$ by N/a_2 etc. One then has the product $a_1 \cdot a_2 \dots a_b$ in the denominator. This will be a large number which may be offset by $1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \dots \cdot b$ at the end of ((14)) we argue.

Thus, it seems that the leading term of Stirling's approximation may be obtained without information theoretic arguments or a saddle point calculation.

Conclusion

We argue that information theoretic arguments may be used to directly obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor. We suggest that there is no particular reason one must maximize the \ln of the number of states subject to a constraint. Rather, the assumption of conservation of energy and a complete loss of information when converting e_1+e_2 into e_i, e_j such that $e_i+e_j=e_1+e_2$ yields $\exp(-e/T)$. This same thinking may be applied to distributing a total E among N particles. If one wishes to have independent probabilities, we suggest $N \rightarrow$ infinite. The set of all E distributions among N particles (microcanonical approach) yields a way of calculating $p(e_i)$. If one considers $p(e_i)$ a priori, then a trial run of $N \rightarrow$ infinite cases, suggests that each $p(e_i)$ appears $Np(e_i)$ times. The average picture is very different from the microcanonical one. Each average trial run has the same probability, and also the same average energy, so we suggest $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ which does not depend on permutations.

The probability of an average trial run ($N \rightarrow$ infinite) should also equal $1 / (N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!)$, i.e. be related to the number of permutations of average runs. Comparing the two approaches allows one to find Stirling's approximation to leading order.

We argue that the approach of independence and $p(e_i)$ power $Np(e_i)$ is implicitly equivalent to $p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. Thus, one may consider maximizing the number of permutations subject to a constraint $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$ with the a priori knowledge that $n(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. This also yields the first order term of Stirling's approximation.

Finally, we suggest that one may obtain $n! = n$ power (n) directly in the $n \rightarrow$ infinite limit, using simply arguments associated with the definition of the factorial.